

Uncertainty in x,t from Special Relativity, Quantum Periodic Wavefunctions and Irrotational Flow

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec. 3. 2024

There appears to be a large interest in the literature (e.g. (1) and many other papers) to linking the quantum Schrodinger equation to fluid flow equations with irrotational fluid flow, defined by $\text{grad } \mathbf{x} \cdot \text{velocity} = 0$. This leads to velocity vector = grad scalar A. Mathematically, grad A is a trivial statement for a constant velocity in that one takes (v_x, v_y, v_z) (where v_x, v_y, v_z are numbers) and multiplies them by x, y, z respectively (i.e. creates a dot product) before using grad to pick out the individual pieces again and make a vector. In other words, for a constant velocity vector, $\mathbf{v} = \text{grad } A$ is a mathematical exercise, not a physical one, unless one considers an object other than $\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{r}$. Nevertheless, quantum mechanics applies to a free particle, even one moving in one dimension and the key idea of quantum physics should be already present in this case.

This means that one no longer really uses $\mathbf{v} = \text{grad } A$, but rather $\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla f(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{x}) = -i d/dx f(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ (in one dimension). This is a different statement from $\mathbf{v} = \text{grad } A$ and the idea of irrotationality. It leads to a periodic function $\exp(i \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ if one does not want the function to grow or diminish indefinitely. In other words, d/dx (or grad) really determines the periodic of function (linked to wavelength) which means that there is uncertainty in x for a given constant v (one dimension). This is completely different physics from irrotational flow, but the math formalism appears to be similar if one considers $\mathbf{v} = \text{grad } A$ in an equation which makes it behave like $\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla f = (-i d/dx f)$. This later statement represents quantum mechanics which is masked as a classical irrotational fluid flow, when it is not, as we have argued before.

As a result, in order to use the "irrotational fluid" approach, one is really stating that there is a periodicity in x and in t linked to \hbar/p and \hbar/E . This implies uncertainties in x and t which would not be present classically. We have argued, however, in previous notes that these uncertainties are already present in $A = -Et + px$ (a Lorentz invariant for constant p, E). In other words, $x = x_0 + \hbar/p$ and $t = t_0 + \hbar/E$ leave A unchanged. This leads to the idea of uncertain x and t regions and again the idea of a periodic function in x and one in t , namely $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$.

As a result, the root of free particle quantum mechanics, we argue, is this uncertainty in x and t which is automatically connected with periodic functions which yield p function, E function), when operated on by $-i d/dx$ and $i d/dt$ partials. The i and f values cancel out in equations and so give the illusion that one simply has $\mathbf{v} = \text{grad } A$ which is linked to irrotational fluid flow, when periodicity and uncertainty is really the key to all of these Schrodinger equation derivations based on fluid flow approaches.

Deriving the Schrodinger Equation from a Fluid Flow Approach

There have been numerous papers in the literature deriving the quantum Schrodinger equation from fluid dynamical approaches because fluid dynamics naturally contains a spatial density as does quantum mechanics, $W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction.

We argue, however, that fluid mechanics is classical and is not based on the idea of uncertainty in x for a constant p and uncertainty in t for a constant E . In other words, for a constant p , the fluid equations and Schrodinger equation should simply yield the classical result:

$$E = p^2/2m \text{ (nonrelativistic). ((1))}$$

((1)) has no appearance of a fluid dynamics equation and so we wish to discuss how these approaches (e.g. (1)) introduce derivatives to obtain the Schrodinger equation and what the real meaning of these derivatives seems to be (according to our arguments).

Irrotational Flow

A key statement used in many fluid dynamics to Schrodinger equation approaches (including (1)) is:

$$\text{Irrotational flow defined by : } \text{grad } \times \text{ velocity} = 0 \rightarrow \text{velocity} = \text{grad } A \text{ ((1))}$$

Here A is a scalar. In the case of a constant velocity, one trivially has irrotationality. In other words, $v = \text{grad } A$ uses $A = r \cdot v$ and then grad to undo the dot product. If one were to only study a constant p (or v) object, which already exhibits quantum mechanics, it seems that no one would ever use $\text{velocity} = \text{grad } A$. This is like taking the number v in one dimension, multiplying it by x and then taking d/dx and arguing that this is the crux of a derivation. Furthermore, quantum mechanics for a constant v already appears in one dimension while the property of irrotationality applies to 3 dimensions. (One can, however, rotate the vector in one dimension.)

The use of $v = \text{grad } A$ is essential in approaches which derive the quantum Schrodinger equation from fluid mechanics and so we wish to determine why this is the case. Our basic idea is that it has nothing to do with irrotationality of a fluid. Rather, it is linked to the notion of periodicity in x, t based on E, p for a constant p , in other words uncertainty in x and t even though E and p are certain. We base our analysis on a free particle because quantum ideas must appear even at this level before considering more complicated cases such as a bound state etc.

Periodicity and Derivatives $d/dt, d/dx$

We argued in the previous section that $v = \text{grad } A$ is a trivial mathematical procedure for a constant v . Taking a number, multiplying by x and then taking d/dx cannot be the crux of deriving the Schrodinger equation. Nevertheless, mathematically the numerous approaches in the literature which use $v = \text{grad } A$ do mathematically obtain the Schrodinger equation from fluid dynamical equations.

We suggest that a very different property is at work. Instead of considering the trivial:

$$d/dx (v x) = v \text{ where } v = \text{number} \text{ ((2))}$$

one considers instead a periodic function with an eigenvalue of v . Actually, we consider a periodic function $F1(Et)$ and $F2(px)$ and use relativistic variables E and p , with $p=\text{constant}$. Thus, the essential equations are:

$$i\frac{d}{dt} F1(Et) = E F1 \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad -i\frac{d}{dx} F2(px) = p F2 \quad ((3b))$$

This leads to $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ as periodic solutions. Thus, one does not really use the irrotational flow equation:

$$V = \text{grad } A, \text{ but rather } ((3a)) \text{ and } ((3b))$$

The “ i ” values easily cancel as do the $F1$ and $F2$ values giving the semblance of $v = \text{grad } A$, when, we argue, completely different physics is present.

What is this physics? A periodic function in t for a constant E and a periodic function in x for a constant p means that there are uncertainty regions \hbar/E and \hbar/p in t and x linked to known values of E, p (constants). This leads to completely different physics from classical physics and has nothing to do with an irrotational fluid, we argue.

Why Should Uncertainty in x and t Appear?

We have argued that the only reason that fluid dynamical approaches yield the Schrodinger equation with the irrotational flow assumption, is that one does not really use this assumption, but rather the notion of a periodic $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. As noted, for a constant v , one would never take a number, multiply it by x , and then take d/dx as the key to creating the Schrodinger equation. It is the key idea of uncertainty in x and t for constant p and E which is the basis of free particle quantum mechanics, we argue.

We have shown in many previous notes that this uncertainty is already present in the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((4))$$

$$A \text{ is degenerate for } t=t_1 + \hbar/E \text{ and } x=x_1 + \hbar/p \quad ((5))$$

This implies, we argue, that there is uncertainty in t and x for constant E, p and leads to the idea of periodic functions needed to describe these regions. This leads to the notion of $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$ and complex probabilities to describe this uncertainty.

Specific Fluid Equations

We list the specific fluid equations used in (1) so that one may see the above ideas at work. First: $v = \text{grad } A$. Then one has:

$$d/dt \text{ partial density} + \text{grad dot (density (grad } A))} = 0 \quad ((5a)) \quad (\text{We drop the vector magnetic potential})$$

$$dA/dt \text{ partial} = -\frac{1}{2} (\text{grad } A) \cdot \text{grad}(A) - V(x) \quad ((5b))$$

For a particle with constant v , $V=0$, density $=1$ and $A = -Et+vx$ (i.e. $m=1$).

In our case, we would argue that:

$$dA/dt \text{ partial is: } i \frac{d}{dt} \text{ partial} \exp(-iEt+px) \text{ so that the } i(-i)=1 \text{ in } ((5b))$$

For $\text{grad}A \cdot \text{grad } A$ where grad is partial grad , A is the argument of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and so could write $(-i)(-i) \text{ grad} \cdot \text{grad} \exp(-iEt+ipx) = \text{grad } A \cdot \text{grad } A$ for a free particle. In the free particle case, $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ cancels from both sides of $((5b))$.

For a bound particle, $W(x,t) = \exp(-iEt) W(x)$, where $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. The arguments for $dA/dt \text{ partial}$ do not change. In this case, $W(x)=\text{density} \exp(-iEt+ipx)$ where $p=0$. We focus our arguments in this note, however, on the free particle case which must yield quantum mechanics without any need of going to the more complicated case of $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that there are numerous approaches in the literature (e.g. (1) etc) which use fluid dynamics, together with the condition of irrotational flow, $v = \text{grad } A$, to derive the Schrodinger equation.

We consider only the case of a free particle which must yield quantum results. We argue that in such a case, $v = \text{grad } A$ is trivial, namely $A = r \cdot p$ and this cannot be the crux for obtaining the Schrodinger equation. In fact, in one dimension, one takes a constant v , multiplies it by x and then takes d/dx . We suggest that the underlying idea at work is one of a periodic function with p as the frequency. In other words, it is not $v = \text{grad } A$ which is the key equation, but rather: $i \frac{d}{dt} \text{ partial} \exp(-iEt+ipx) = E \exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and $-i \frac{d}{dx} \text{ partial} \exp(-iEt+ipx) = p \exp(-iEt+ipx)$ ((BB)). This represents different physics from classical physics because a constant E implies an uncertainty region in t and a constant p , an uncertainty region in x . These quantum features already appear from the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ which is degenerate for $x=x_1+h\bar{h}/p$ and $t=t_1+h\bar{h}/E$. In fact, the A of fluid approach is linked to $-Et+px$. Thus, we suggest that $v = \text{grad } A$ has the same appearance of the more complicated and physically different ((BB)) equations and that the quantum result is based on x, t uncertainty and not irrotational flow.

References

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